

Synthesis and reduction of nitrones of 2-chlorobenzaldehyde and their antifungal potential

Balbir Kaur Matharu^a, J. R. Sharma^b and M. R. Manrao^{a*}

^aDepartment of Biochemistry and Chemistry, ^bDepartment of Plant Pathology,
Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana-141 004, India

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Condensation of 2-chlorobenzaldehyde with phenylhydroxylamines resulted in the formation of *C*-(2-chlorophenyl)-*N*-phenylnitrones (**1a-6a**) which were characterized on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral studies. Sodium borohydride reduction of the nitrones was carried out and the nitrones were screened for their antifungal potential against five phytopathogenic fungi.

Schiff bases have been extensively studied for their biological activity¹, whereas very little work had been reported regarding the biological activity of nitrones². This paper describes the synthesis of nitrones from 2-chlorobenzaldehyde, their spectral data, reduction and antifungal potential.

Results and discussion

The solids obtained by the condensation of 2-chlorobenzaldehyde with phenylhydroxylamine and substituted phenylhydroxylamines (**1-6**) have been identified as *C*-(2-chlorophenyl)-*N*-(phenyl)nitronone (**1a**), *C*-(2-chlorophenyl)-*N*-(4-chlorophenyl)nitronone (**2a**), *C*-(2-chlorophenyl)-*N*-(3-chlorophenyl)nitronone (**3a**), *C*-(2-chlorophenyl)-*N*-(2-chlorophenyl)nitronone (**4a**), *C*-(2-chlorophenyl)-*N*-(4-methylphenyl)nitronone (**5a**) and *C*-(2-chlorophenyl)-*N*-(3-methylphenyl)nitronone (**6a**) respectively on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral studies.

The infrared spectra of the compounds contain bands at ~1600 and 1260 cm⁻¹ which indicate the presence of carbon-nitrogen double bond and N → O linkage respectively. The PMR spectrum of **6a** in CDCl₃ indicates a three protons singlet at δ 2.4 which is assigned to methyl protons, a multiplet between δ 7.2–8.3 for eight aromatic protons and one proton singlet at δ 8.9 for azomethinic proton. The mass spectrum of **3a** gives molecular ion peak at *m/e* 266 and the base peak is obtained at *m/e* 111 due to the species ClC₆H₄.

Sodium borohydride reduction of nitrones **1a-6a** at room temperature yielded the corresponding Schiff bases **1b-6b** (Scheme 1). Upon raising the temperature to 50–60°C, the Schiff bases (**1b-6b**) were further reduced to the corresponding secondary amines (**1c-6c**). The Schiff

Scheme 1. Synthesis of nitrones and their sodium borohydride reduction.

bases and secondary amines were identified on the basis of m.p., m.m.p., elemental analysis and comparison of IR and PMR spectra of those of authentic samples.

Antifungal activity: The nitrones (**1a-6a**) were screened *in vitro* for their antifungal activity against *Alternaria alternata*, *Fusarium oxysporum*, *Ustilago tritici*, *Helminthosporium gramineum* and *Myrothecium roridum* by spore germination inhibition method³. Only one of the test compounds (**6a**) has ED₅₀ value less than 1000 ppm against *F. oxysporum*. The nitronone **1a** has been found to be quite effective in controlling *H. gramineum*. Four compounds have ED₅₀ values less than 1000 ppm against *A. alternata* and the most effective among them is **2a** with

ED₅₀ value of 280 ppm. All the test compounds have exhibited moderate activity against *U. tritici*. Except compound **1a**, the synthesized nitrones have been shown to possess promising activity against *M. roridum* with the compound **4a** having ED₅₀ value of 65 ppm against this fungus. Two more compounds of interest are **2a** and **6a** which possess ED₅₀ values of 120 ppm and 140 ppm, respectively against *M. roridum*. Only one compound (**6a**) has shown moderate to promising activity against all the test fungi.

Experimental

All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis and the melting points are uncorrected.

Synthesis of nitrones : 2-Chlorobenzaldehyde (0.1 mol) was dissolved in chloroform in a conical flask (500 ml). Phenylhydroxylamine/substituted phenylhydroxylamine (0.1 mol), prepared by the reduction of nitrobenzene/substituted nitrobenzene with zinc dust and ammonium chloride was added to the above solution with stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at the room temperature. Excess of solvent was then removed and the contents were cooled. The solid, which separated out was filtered and crystallized from methanol to get respective nitrone with m.p. (°C) and % yield : **1a** (240, 69); **2a** (112, 53); **3a** (88, 58); **4a** (77, 85); **5a** (68, 53) and **6a** (63,65).

Reaction with sodium borohydride : Sodium borohydride (2 g) was added in small instalments to a solution of C-(2-chlorophenyl)-N-phenylnitronone/its N-phenyl derivative (**1a-6a**) (0.01 mol) in methanol (50 ml) with stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature. It was then diluted with water and extracted with chloroform. Removal of solvent gave the crude prod-

uct, which was crystallized from ethanol to get respective Schiff base with m.p. (°C) and % yield : **1b** (35, 65); **2b** (52, 60); **3b** (40, 70); **4b** (110, 75); **5b** (50, 60) and **6b** (oil, 80).

The reaction mixture when warmed to 60°C, the Schiff base (**1b-6b**) was further reduced to the respective secondary amine with m.p. (°C) and % yield : **1c** (40, 60); **2c** (40, 58); **3c** (48, 55); **4c** (38, 78); **5c** (45, 74) and **6c** (oil, 80).

In vitro testing of nitrones for antifungal activity : Each compound (20 mg) was dissolved in ethanol (0.5 ml) and sterilized distilled water (9.5 ml) was then added to prepare the stock solution (2000 ppm). The stock solutions were serially diluted to obtain the required concentration of the compounds. The suspension of the test fungus was mixed separately with the solution/suspension of the compounds in equal amount in the cavities of the cavity slides. These slides were kept in petriplates lined with moist filter paper and incubated for 20 h at 25 ± 1°C. The slides were checked for percent germination occurred and percent spore germination inhibition was calculated. Antifungal activity has been expressed in terms of ED₅₀ values (effective dose to inhibit 50% spore germination) calculated by log probability method³.

References

1. D. N. Dhar and C. L. Taploo, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1982, **41**, 501; M. R. Manrao and Sunita Kohli, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **63**, 410; M. R. Manrao, R. K. Sethi, R. C. Sharma and P. S. Kalsi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 695.
2. M. Thirumalaikumar, S. Shivasubramanian, A. Ponnuswamy and P. Mohan, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 1996, **31**, 905.
3. T. S. Thind, C. Mohan, Prem Raj and J. K. Arora, *Indian Phytopath.*, 2004, **57**, 104.